

Paleogeographic origin of the wild taxa in the genus *Oryza* and their genomic relationships

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My recent postulate that the progenitors and wild relatives of the Asian and African cultivars *O. sativa* and *O. glaberrima* originated in the humid tropics of the Gondwanaland continents (Euphytica 25:425–441, 1976) not only can explain the pan-tropical distribution of the above taxa that have the *AA* genome in common but could also relate the geographic distribution of other wild species in the genus to their genomic composition.

Those taxa on the western component of the supercontinent (now South America) – *O. alta*, *O. grandiglumis*, and *O. latifolia* – have the *CCDD* genomes.

The other taxa – *O. eichingeri*, *O. punctata*, *O. minuta*, and *O. officinalis* located on the eastern components of Gondwanaland (now the Indian subcontinent, Southeast Asia mainland, the east coast of Africa, and Malagasy) – have *BB*, *CC*, or *BBCC* genomes.

The Australian-based *O. australiensis* (genome *EE*) and the African-based *O. brachyantha* (*FF*) do not readily fit into the pattern of continental drift.

The genomes of the remaining Asian species, *O. granulata*, *O. longiglumis*, *O. meyeriana*, *O. ridleyi*, and *O. schlecteri*, remain to be determined.

Cytogenetic evidence indicates that partial homology exists between the *A* and *B* genomes and between the *A* and *C* genomes.

Prospects of rice breeding in Kerala state, India

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Thirty-four rice strains have been evolved by pure-line selection from the most popular local varieties in Kerala state, India. A few strains were intended for S. Kanara district of Karnataka state. Seventeen are suited to the first crop season and nine to the second. Ptb 10 is early maturing, suited for all

Cultures from promising crosses of intermediate height, Kerala state, India.

Pedigree	Cultures (no.)
Triveni/IR2071-251-1-1-3	42
Jaya/IR2058/Mahsuri	120
Jaya/IR2153/Bhavani	80
Jaya/IR2071/Mahsuri	115
Jaya/IR2153/Mahsuri	82
Jaya/IR2153/23178	16
<i>Blast-resistant cultures</i>	
Triveni/IR1857-78-1-3	26
Jyothi/IR1857-78-1-3	30
Triveni/IR1702-74-3	8
Jyothi/IR2153-479-2-3	58
Jaya/IR2071-179-9-5	52
Bharathi/IR2071-25-1-1-3	8
<i>Sheath blight-resistant cultures</i>	
Jaya/S1 56	22
Triveni/S1 56	8
Jyothi/S1 56	4
<i>BPH-tolerant cultures</i>	
Bharathi/IR2071-625-3-1	103
Triveni/Mudgo	75
Triveni/IR2061-464	95
Triveni/IR1539	126

three seasons. Ptb 18 and 21, resistant to stem borer and gall midge, are being utilized in breeding programs. Ptb 28, 29, and 30 are suitable for dry land (*modan*) conditions as a purely rainfed crop for the first crop season. Ptb 33 is resistant to brown planthoppers. Chennellu is a mass-selected variety suitable for shade (e.g. under coconut trees).

An intensive breeding program to combine desirable traits of local varieties with the high yield potential of the dwarf *indicas* began in 1964. Since then, seven high yielding rice varieties have been released for various agroclimatic regions of the state. The first Indian semidwarf variety Annapoora, from the cross Ptb 10/TN1, is red grained and early maturing. It has enjoyed unprecedented popularity in Kerala and has spread to parts of Tamil Nadu and Sri Lanka. It was followed by Aswathy, Rohini, Triveni, Sabari, Bharathi, and Jyothi.

Varieties already released and many of the promising cultures lack multiple resistance to diseases and pests. Future varieties should have moderate resistance to sheath blight, blast, and bacterial blight, and some ability to withstand the attack of brown planthoppers, stem borers, and leaf folders. Varieties that can be grown under minimum plant protection schedules have to be selected and, to provide straw, they should be

nonlodging varieties of intermediate height. From over 120 crosses, cultures promising in such qualities are under test. They are mainly from the crosses listed in the table.

Rices for late plantings in India

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Tank-fed rice is grown on about 120,000 ha in Karnataka state, India, with paddy cultivation beginning in September and October. Because most of the vegetative and reproductive periods are exposed to low temperatures, yields are relatively low. Diseases are also more severe in such late plantings. We sought to identify comparatively disease-free and cold-tolerant varieties and cultures for areas where late planting is practiced.

Twenty-eight varieties and cultures were sown at Hebbal and at Mandya in the third week of August and again in the third week of September 1973. Three-week-old seedlings were planted in two replications in 3.6- x 3.0-m plots following a randomized block design. Observations for diseases were made at tillering and milky stages.

At Hebbal, some varieties showed susceptibility to blast, bacterial blight, bacterial leaf streak, and cold injury. Varieties S 317 and S 705 were susceptible to all three diseases. MR 249, 263, 271, 274, 275, 276, 277, 278, 280, 281, 288, Ch 2, Ch 45, CR 126-27-13, CR 126-53-1, Madhu, and Sona were moderately susceptible to bacterial blight or bacterial leaf streak, or both.

At Mandya, incidence of bacterial leaf blight and bacterial leaf streak was lower than at Hebbal. Blast incidence was as high as at Hebbal on S 317 and S 705.

Nine varieties and cultures were selected as having moderate resistance to blast, bacterial blight, bacterial leaf streak, and cold injury. They are MR 272, MR 273, MR 279, MR 283, MR 65-1, CR 126-33-11, CR 126-42-1, IR20, and IEL 2295.